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Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Prevention/ Preventive chemotherapies

Section

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Title

Mass relapse prevention for malaria caused by *Plasmodium vivax*

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Mass relapse prevention for malaria caused by *Plasmodium vivax*

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Summary of findings table

Mass relapse prevention (MRP) compared to no MRP for reducing transmission of *Plasmodium vivax*

Patient or population: People of all ages living in areas ongoing to potential *P. vivax* transmission

Setting: Areas with ongoing or potential *P. vivax* transmission

Intervention: Mass relapse prevention

Comparison: No mass relapse prevention

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with no MRP	Risk with MRP				
Incidence of <i>P. vivax</i> <1 month post-MRP	36 per 1,000 person-years	3 per 1,000 (2 to 3)	Rate ratio 0.07 (0.05 to 0.08)	813232 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW a,b,c,d	We do not know if MRP has an effect on incidence of <i>P. vivax</i> at <1 month post-MRP
Incidence of <i>P. vivax</i> 1-3 months post-MRP	111 per 1,000 person-years	9 per 1,000 (8 to 9)	Rate ratio 0.08 (0.07 to 0.08)	873232 (2 observational studies)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW c,d,e,f	We do not know if MRP has an effect on incidence of <i>P. vivax</i> at 1-3 months post-MRP
Incidence of <i>P. vivax</i> 4-12 months post-MRP	13 per 1,000 person-years	3 per 1,000 (2 to 3)	Rate ratio 0.20 (0.18 to 0.22)	873232 (2 observational studies)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW c,d,e,f	We do not know if MRP has an effect on incidence of <i>P. vivax</i> at 4-12 months post-MRP
Prevalence of <i>P. vivax</i> parasitemia <1 month post-MRP	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to <u>4</u>)	RR 1.45 (<u>0.13</u> to <u>150.95</u>)	<u>88549353</u> (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW a,b,c,dg	We do not know if MRP has an effect on <i>P. vivax</i> parasitemia prevalence at <1 month post-MRP
Prevalence of <i>P. vivax</i> parasitemia 4-12 months post-MRP	4 per 1,000	3-0 per 1,000 (<u>2-0</u> to <u>7</u>)	RR 0.90 (<u>0.01</u> to <u>1.99</u>)	<u>72096710</u> (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW a,b,c,dh	We do not know if MRP has an effect on <i>P. vivax</i> parasitemia prevalence at 4-12 months post-MRP
Adverse events	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	333946 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW a,b,ig,jh	We do not know if MRP has an effect on adverse events.

***The risk in the intervention group** (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI). For incidence outcomes, the absolute rates were determined using person-time rather than population as the denominator.

CI: Confidence interval; **MRP:** Mass relapse prevention; **RR:** Risk ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: We are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect

Moderate certainty: We are moderately confident in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different

Low certainty: Our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect

Very low certainty: We have very little confidence in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect

Explanations

a. Downgraded by 1 due to risk of bias. Quasi-experimental study design with a control group, but allocation was not done at random and no baseline data were provided to assess potential confounders.

b. Not downgraded for inconsistency due to single study result

c. Not downgraded for indirectness since evidence was judged to be sufficiently direct for the domains of population, intervention, comparator, direct comparison, and outcome

d. Not downgraded for imprecision since lower and upper confidence limits indicate the same direction of effect.

e. Downgraded by 2 due to risk of bias. Many risk of bias domains judged as high risk or not enough information to determine. High risk of bias due to confounding in both studies included for this outcome.

f. Not downgraded for inconsistency. Both studies provided the same direction and a similar magnitude (qualitatively) of effect.

~~g. Downgraded by 2 due to high imprecision as a result of few cases. Confidence intervals span values for a very large effect in both directions.~~

~~h. Downgraded by 1 due to imprecision. Confidence intervals span values in both directions.~~

~~ig.~~ Downgraded by 2 due to indirectness. Side effects were not measured or reported in the control group, so evidence is only provided in the intervention population.

~~jh.~~ Not downgraded for imprecision since this criteria is not applicable for this outcome (no effect measure presented).

Background

Malaria is a parasitic disease transmitted to humans through the bite of an infected female *Anopheles* mosquito and is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Malaria caused by *Plasmodium vivax* presents a unique challenge to elimination efforts due to the parasite's ability to remain dormant in the liver and cause future relapses [1].¹ Strains of *P. vivax* from different geographical areas have been shown to have different relapse periodicity, with strains from tropical regions relapsing more quickly than those from temperate regions [3]. Although treatment with 8-aminoquinoline antimalarial drugs (e.g., primaquine and tafenoquine [4]) can effectively clear hypnozoites and prevent relapse (radical cure), this class of antimalarials may increase the risk of acute hemolytic anemia (AHA) in people with glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency [5], who are more likely to reside in malaria-endemic areas [6]. The increased risk in AHA is dependent on the severity of the G6PD deficiency and on the dose of medication given. In some settings where the severity and prevalence of G6PD deficiency is low, and the relapse periodicity is long, mass treatment with primaquine (e.g. mass primaquine prophylactic treatment [MPPT]) during the low transmission season has been used to reduce subsequent *P. vivax* transmission by preventing relapses during periods when mosquito densities increased [7]. As primaquine is no longer the only 8-aminoquinoline recommended for radical cure of *P. vivax*, mass relapse prevention (MRP) is defined as the administration of an 8-aminoquinoline without the co-administration of schizonticidal therapy to the entire population in a defined geographic area, irrespective of infection status, to reduce *P. vivax* transmission.

This systematic synthesis of available evidence and contextual considerations can inform the development of World Health Organization guidelines on the use of mass relapse prevention to reduce *P. vivax* transmission.

Objectives

Main objectives

1. To synthesize evidence about the efficacy of giving an 8-aminoquinoline (an antimalarial medication that clears hypnozoites or dormant liver stage parasites) at approximately the same time to reduce transmission of *P. vivax* in people residing in delimited geographic areas with ongoing or potential *P. vivax* transmission (i.e. mass relapse prevention)
2. To synthesize evidence about the safety of mass relapse prevention with an 8-aminoquinoline when given to people residing in delimited geographic areas with ongoing or potential *P. vivax* transmission

Secondary objectives

1. To summarize evidence on contextual factors for mass relapse prevention with a hypnozoitocidal drug. Contextual factors include the valuation of the outcomes of interest, and the societal implications, impact on equity, resource use, acceptability, and feasibility of the intervention of interest.

¹ *P. ovale* is another malaria parasite that has a dormant liver stage, but this parasite is rarely found outside of Africa, and comprises <1% of malaria infections where it is found [2]. Okafor CNF, N. A.: **Plasmodium Ovale Malaria**. In: *StatPearls*. edn. Treasure Island (FL); 2020.]

2. To summarize findings from mathematical modeling studies with respect to the impact of different operational factors on the modeled efficacy of mass relapse prevention, including optimal timing with respect to malaria transmission seasons, number of rounds, time between rounds, minimum coverage, and number of years.

Methods

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of study to be included

For the main objectives, the following study designs were included:

- Randomized designs
 - Cluster-randomized controlled trials (cRCTs) with at least two clusters per arm
 - Cluster-randomized cross over trials with: (a) at least two clusters per arm and (b) a suitable washout period during which the intervention is no longer applied
 - Cluster-randomized stepped wedge designs with at least four clusters
 - Cluster-randomized factorial designs with at least two clusters per level
- Non-randomized designs
 - Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials
 - Controlled before-and-after studies (CBAs) with a contemporaneous control group
 - Interrupted time series (ITS) studies with: (a) a clearly defined point in time when the intervention occurred, and (b) at least three data points collected both before the first round of mass relapse prevention and at least three data points collected after the last round of mass relapse prevention, measured at evenly spaced intervals (i.e. monthly).
 - Due to the seasonality of malaria transmission, if pre- and post-intervention data points are measured at different calendar months (i.e. different periods of the transmission season), a sensitivity analysis was planned to explore the potential bias introduced by including these studies.
 - Uncontrolled before-and-after studies or before-and-after studies with historical controls (if included, a sensitivity analysis will be performed)

We excluded studies if we observed the following:

- For studies with a control group:
 - The follow-up periods for the intervention and control periods were not identical
 - The timing of baseline and/or endline surveys differed in intervention and control groups
 - The length of pre- and post-intervention periods differed for ITS studies
 - Background interventions were not equally implemented between intervention and control arms or were implemented at different times

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For the secondary objectives, all study designs including qualitative and economic evaluations were considered to synthesize contextual information. Mathematical modeling studies were included to inform operational parameters; their results were summarized to determine whether they supported findings of the systematic review or not.

Types of participants

All adults and children living in a delimited geographic area with ongoing or potential *P. vivax* transmission are the population of interest. We included studies in special groups (i.e. refugees and soldiers) if they met eligibility criteria and constitute the entire population of a delimited geographic area.

Types of interventions

Intervention arm

Mass relapse prevention was defined as the direct administration of a full therapeutic course (minimum of 3.5 mg/kg total dose) of an antimalarial medicine that targets liver-stage parasites (i.e. an 8-aminoquinoline, currently only primaquine or tafenoquine) at the same time, without the administration of a schizonticide, to the entire eligible population of a defined geographic area, irrespective of the presence of symptoms or infection. Due to safety considerations, persons ineligible to take an 8-aminoquinoline generally include pregnant or lactating women, children <6 months and people with known G6PD deficiency. We excluded studies of chemoprevention in the form of individually-timed intermittent preventive treatment in sub-populations (i.e. pregnant women, children or infants), seasonal chemoprevention (without an 8-aminoquinoline), and mass relapse prevention targeted to a subset of the population based on age, occupation, or another demographic characteristic. Studies of mass drug administration (MDA) with both a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoitocidal drug were excluded from this review but were included in a separate review on MDA.

Control arm (for designs with a control group)

The control group for cluster-randomized trials included populations that did not receive any intervention or were administered a placebo; the control group for a CBA was the pre-intervention period; the control period for an ITS study was the pre-intervention time period up to one year prior to intervention.

Background interventions

Studies where additional malaria interventions considered standard of care were implemented were included as long as interventions (both malaria and non-malaria) were balanced between intervention and control arms. Ideally, the population coverage levels of all other malaria and non-malaria co-interventions should be similar in both arms at baseline and were noted during data extraction.

Types of outcome measures

Studies reported at least one of the following to be included: one or more outcomes, data on contextual factors, or mathematical modeling results for variation in operational parameters. For outcomes that specified parasitological confirmation, the possible diagnostic approaches included malaria rapid diagnostic tests (RDT), microscopy, or molecular methods such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

Outcomes

Critical outcomes were measured at the population-level as this intent is to reduce transmission community wide. However, certain outcomes could also be measured among those receiving the intervention. If outcomes were reported for unspecified *Plasmodium* species, the local epidemiology of the study area was used to infer the predominant species and a secondary analysis was conducted to explore effects on malaria caused by *P. vivax*. The following outcomes as defined were assessed:

- **Incidence of malaria infection or number of indigenous malaria cases:** parasitologically-confirmed malaria infections from active and/or passive surveillance in a cohort
- **Prevalence of malaria infection:** measured in a cross-sectional survey with parasitologic confirmation
- **Interruption of transmission:** defined as 0 indigenous or local malaria cases following the last round of mass relapse prevention for some period during the putative transmission season
- **Incidence of clinical malaria:** febrile illness with parasitologically-confirmed malaria infection from passive surveillance or in a cohort

Among those receiving the intervention:

- **Adverse events,** including acute hemolysis or AHA

Contextual factors

Evidence for the following contextual factors were summarized if available:

- **Values and preferences.** This describes the relative importance assigned to health outcomes by those affected by them; how such importance varies within and across populations; and whether this importance or variability is surrounded by uncertainty.
- **Acceptability:** the extent to which those benefiting from an intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the *intervention* to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention
- **Health equity, equality and non-discrimination:** the extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, SES status, residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all
- **Financial and economic considerations:** the cost, overall economic impact, cost-benefit, and/or cost-effectiveness
- **Feasibility and health system considerations:** barriers to implementation (i.e., resources available, programmatic considerations, existing and necessary infrastructure), interaction with existing health system, need for and use of the existing health workforce (including training)

Operational parameters

Insights from mathematical modeling on how variation in operational parameters alter the effectiveness of mass relapse prevention were summarized for at least the following parameters if available:

- Timing of rounds with respect to the transmission season
- Number of rounds
- Spacing of rounds
- Number of years for the intervention

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- Coverage
- Adherence
- Dosage and dosage schedule

Timing of outcome measurement

The pre-intervention or baseline period was defined as 1-12 months prior to, or time period concurrent with, the first round of mass relapse prevention (with the exception of ITS, which is defined above).

The post-intervention period refers to the time period following the *last round* of mass relapse prevention. For studies with a single round of mass relapse prevention, the *last round* referred to the time period following the round. For studies with multiple rounds, the *last round* referred to the last round that occurred during a given transmission season (last round of the first year).

- Subsequent mass relapse prevention rounds that were administered in a second year were treated as a new analysis period.

For analysis, data were pooled into the following post-intervention time period categories, if available: <1 month, 1-3 months, 4 to <12 months and 12-24 months following the *last round* of mass relapse prevention. If multiple data points were available within the same time period category and data could not be combined (i.e. non-independent samples for prevalence or different cohorts for incidence), then the latest measure was used.

Search methods for identification of studies

Literature searches were not restricted to specific study designs or restricted by date. All studies that met the eligibility criteria, regardless of language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, and in progress), were included.

Electronic database searches

We searched the following databases using the search terms and strategy described in Appendix 2 for articles from 2012 onwards: Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register; Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The Cochrane Library; MEDLINE (Pubmed); EMBASE (OVID); and LILACS. We also searched the WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP; <http://www.who.int/ictrp/en/>) and ClinicalTrials.gov (<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/home>) for trials in progress, using “malaria” and “mass drug administration” as search terms.

For articles prior to 2012, we screened both included and excluded articles identified from a Cochrane Review on MDA published in 2013 [8]. The Cochrane MDA Review used a similar database search strategy as described in Appendix 2 and the search was updated in February 2013 prior to publication.

Searching other resources

Reference lists

Additionally, we screened the reference lists of all eligible studies and articles identified by the above methods and those listed in review articles [8-12] for additional relevant studies.

Conference proceedings

We searched the following recent proceedings for relevant abstracts: Sixth Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Durban, South Africa; October 2013), Seventh Multilateral

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Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Dakar, Senegal; April 2018), American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) 62nd Annual Meeting (Washington, DC, USA; November 2013), ASTMH 63rd Annual Meeting (New Orleans, LA, USA; November 2014), ASTMH 64th Annual Meeting (Philadelphia, PA, USA; October 2015), ASTMH 65th Annual Meeting (Atlanta, GA, USA; November 2016), ASTMH 66th Annual Meeting (Baltimore, MD, USA; November 2017), ASTMH 67th Annual Meeting (New Orleans, LA, USA; October 2018), and ASTMH 68th Annual Meeting (National Harbor, MD, USA; November 2019).

Researchers and organizations

In addition to the electronic searches described above, we consulted with the Malaria Elimination Initiative at the University of California at San Francisco and other relevant groups to identify both published and unpublished studies that might be available from other sources. We also contacted the Malaria Eradication Research Agenda Consortium, the Malaria Eradication Scientific Alliance, and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.

Data collection and analysis

Selection of studies

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts identified from literature searches based on the pre-determined inclusion criteria. Potentially relevant articles identified by both reviewers were evaluated by the same two reviewers for full-text eligibility based on the pre-determined inclusion criteria. A third reviewer was consulted to resolve any disagreements by discussion or consensus. All Russian language articles were reviewed by a native Russian speaker (NW) to determine eligibility. At the full-text stage, we collated different publications reporting on the same study. Full-text studies that did not meet eligibility criteria are listed with their reasons for exclusion in the [Characteristics of excluded studies](#) table. The result of the study selection process was summarized in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow diagram.

Data extraction and management

Two reviewers independently extracted information from studies on a pre-piloted electronic data extraction form. Any discrepancies in information were resolved by discussion to reach consensus or by consultation with a third reviewer. A native Russian speaker extracted data from articles written in Russian. We contacted the original study author(s) for any missing data or for clarifications.

The following information were extracted:

- **Study design and setting:** dates of study, location of study, baseline malaria endemicity (prevalence or incidence), description of malaria seasonality, malaria species, vector species, antimalarial drug resistance context, study design type; method of randomization (if applicable), and statistical power.
 - For cRCTs: unit of randomization, adjustment for clustering and method used, intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC), number of clusters randomized and analyzed, number of participants, average cluster size, and features of the clusters (i.e., matching or buffer areas)
- **Participants:** Age groups and other demographic features of the population were included and the population targeted by arm.

- **Intervention:** mass relapse prevention drug and dose, coverage, timing (number of rounds/campaigns, dates of rounds, duration implemented, and timing relative to malaria transmission season). Also, baseline coverage of malaria co-interventions in both intervention and control arms were recorded as well as adherence to the course of treatment if available.
- **Outcomes:** definition and measurement (including malaria diagnostic or surveillance method, population in which outcome was measured, and length of follow-up if relevant), time point(s) at which outcome was assessed in relation to mass relapse prevention rounds, sample size, incomplete outcomes or missing data.
- **Contextual factors:** information on contextual factors (as defined under “Types of outcome measures”) were extracted from studies and summarized, but these data were not included in meta-analyses.

For dichotomous outcomes (prevalence), we extracted the number of prevalent cases and number of participants in each study arm. For rate data (incidence), we extracted the number of events, the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm, and a measure of variance (standard error). For continuous data, we extracted the mean and a measure of variance (standard deviation).

For cluster RCTs we recorded the measure of effect (such as risk ratio [RR], odds ratio, rate ratio, or mean difference [MD]) with confidence intervals (CI) or standard deviations.

For non-randomized studies, we extracted adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempt to control for confounding including RRs and rate ratios.

For ITS designs, the number of malaria cases or incidence were extracted at available time points and categorized by time period (pre-intervention, during intervention, and post-intervention). If data on the number of malaria tests performed or population size were available, these were extracted as well at the same time points.

We included pre-intervention data up to one year prior to the intervention. Post-intervention data were extracted at the time points specified.

Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

Two members of the review team independently assessed the risk of bias for each study that met eligibility criteria using a tool designed to assess such risk and generated an overall assessment reported as low, moderate, serious, critical or unclear, and summary graphs to display results. As the risk of bias in the effect of an intervention may be different for different outcomes, a ‘Risk of bias’ assessment for each outcome were made. We resolved any discrepancies through discussion or by consulting a third member of the review team.

For each included RCT, the revised Cochrane ‘Risk of bias’ tool was planned to be used [13]. We assessed non-randomized studies and ITS trials for risk of bias using key criteria summarized from a variety of risk of bias assessments for observational studies [14]. Uncontrolled before-and-after studies were assigned a high risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.

Strategy for data synthesis

Measures of treatment effect

To calculate incidence of parasitemia, the denominator was the person-time of observation, calculated as the size of the study or observed population multiplied by the number of months of observation and divided by 12 to calculate person-years.

For study designs with a contemporaneous control group, the effect of the intervention was compared using RRs if the outcome was dichotomous, rate ratios if the outcome is a rate, and MD for continuous measures. All effects are presented with their 95% CIs. For before and after comparisons, the pre-intervention measurement was calculated during the same calendar months as the post-intervention comparison to minimize seasonal differences.

For ITS designs, time series regression models adjusting for temporal correlation (by Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average [ARIMA]) was planned to be used to model post-intervention effects. Predicted values at the specified post-intervention time points were estimated from Poisson or negative binomial regression (determined by model fit) fitted to pre-intervention malaria cases and including number of malaria tests or population size as an offset term. Two effect sizes were estimated from the output of these models: a change in level (difference between observed level at the first post-intervention time point and the model predicted level at the same time point; “immediate effect”) and a change in slope (difference between post- and pre- intervention slopes; “longer term effect” of the intervention) [15-17].

Unit of analysis issues

For cRCTs, measures of effect adjusted for clustering were used if available and when possible, otherwise, we planned to adjust the raw data using ICC values obtained from the study or authors or obtained from similar studies.

If studies had multiple intervention arms, treatment arms were combined if appropriate, or participants in the control group split so that they were only included once in the meta-analysis [18].

For randomized cross-over trials if included, the methods outlined in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions were applied [19].

Dealing with missing data

We attempted to contact study authors to obtain any missing data. No data imputation was applied; however, several options were considered for the handling of missing data [20-22].

Assessment of heterogeneity

We assessed heterogeneity by examining forest plots for overlapping CIs. Statistical heterogeneity was examined using the I^2 statistic and classified according to the criteria below:

- Moderate: I^2 between 30% and 60%
- Substantial: I^2 values between 50% and 90%
- Considerable: I^2 values between 75% and 100%

If there was substantial heterogeneity (I^2 statistic value above 50%) and inconsistency in the direction of the effect with non-overlapping CIs, then we did not perform a meta-analysis.

Assessment of reporting biases

If ten or more studies are included, reporting bias would be examined using funnel plots and analyzed visually for asymmetry and using formal tests for funnel plot asymmetry [23].

Data synthesis

Data from randomized and non-randomized studies were pooled separately. We used random-effects meta-analysis to report a pooled effect estimate when appropriate. If there are only two studies available for synthesis, fixed-effect meta-analysis was used if meta-analysis was appropriate.

Certainty of the evidence

Randomized trials (e.g. cluster RCTs, randomized cross-over trials, stepped wedge cluster randomized trials) started at a high certainty of evidence but could be downgraded for valid reasons within the following five categories: risk of bias, imprecision, inconsistency, indirectness, and publication bias. Non-randomized studies (e.g. CBAs, ITS) started at a low certainty of evidence but could be upgraded if there was a large or a dose response effect, and if all plausible residual confounding would have reduced a demonstrated effect or would have suggested a spurious effect if no effect was observed [24]. The certainty of evidence and results are summarized in the [Summary of findings table](#) [25-27].

The certainty of the body of evidence for each outcome was evaluated using the GRADE approach [25] and each outcome was rated as described by Balshem et. al. [24].

- High: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.
- Moderate: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect.
- Low: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited. The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
- Very low: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Subgroup analysis

Although no sub-group analyses were examined, the following potential effect modifiers were included in the protocol:

- Transmission level (very low-to-low, moderate-to-high)
- Level of vector control coverage at baseline ($\geq 80\%$ vs $<80\%$)
- Use of G6PD testing to guide treatment (yes/no)
- Medication used (primaquine or tafenoquine)
- Coverage of the intervention ($\geq 80\%$ vs $<80\%$)
- *P. vivax* strain (temperate vs. tropical)
- Timing of the intervention with respect to the transmission season.

Sensitivity analysis

We planned to perform sensitivity analysis to explore the effect of exclusion of studies at high risk of bias (for allocation concealment, incomplete outcome data or critical risk of bias due to study design) on the overall results if appropriate.

If the ICC value was estimated, we planned to undertake sensitivity analyses to investigate the impact of varying the ICC value on meta-analysis results.

Results

Description of studies

Included and excluded studies are described in detail in the [Characteristics of studies](#) tables.

Results of the search

A total of 904 articles were identified from searching electronic databases, registers, and other sources: 740 records from database search from 2012 onwards (11 November 2020), 154 from previous Cochrane Reviews on MDA ([8, 28]), and an additional 10 from other sources. After de-duplication, 866 articles were screened against title and abstract eligibility and, of these, 25 were assessed for full-text eligibility criteria (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

Included studies

Two non-randomized studies met criteria for inclusion: one quasi-experimental cluster-controlled study (**Pant 2014** [29]) conducted in the Democratic People's Republic of Korea (DPRK) and one uncontrolled before-and-after study (**Rybalka 1979** [30]) conducted in Azerbaijan Soviet Socialist Republic (ASSR). Additionally, one mathematical modeling study (**Roy 2013** [31]) was identified. Baseline *P. vivax*

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prevalence in **Pant 2014** [29] was reported as <1%. No baseline malaria prevalence data were available for **Rybalka 1979**. Descriptive characteristics for the two studies reporting empirical data are summarized in **Table 1** and described in detail in [Characteristics of included studies](#).

Table 1. Summary characteristics of included studies

Study (location)	Year(s) of study	Study design	Mass relapse prevention (MRP)		Outcomes reported (months of follow-up post-MRP)
			Rounds, interval, duration, seasonality	Population targeted (coverage)	
Pant 2014 [29] (Democratic People's Republic of Korea)	2002	Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trial, no pre-intervention data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primaquine administered for 14 days (0.25 mg/kg per day) 1 round administered over 2 weeks (April 18-May 3, 2002), just prior to the peak transmission season (May-August) 	391,357 (85%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incidence – monthly (1-5 months post-MRP) Prevalence (<1 month and 4 months post-MRP) Adverse events Contextual factors: feasibility and health system considerations
Rybalka 1979 [30] (Azerbaijan Soviet Socialist Republic)	1970-71	Uncontrolled before-and-after study (pre-intervention data used as control)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primaquine administered for 14 days (dose likely to be 0.25 mg/kg per day) 1 round administered over 3 months (April-June), just prior to the peak transmission season (ND) 	30,000 (ND)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incidence – monthly (<1-10 months post-MRP)

Notes: ND = not described

Interventions

Both studies administered a single round of MRP with primaquine for 14 days (0.25 mg/kg mg per day in **Pant 2014** [29], dose not described in **Rybalka 1979** [30] but inferred from **Kondrashin 2014** as 0.25 mg/kg per day). The single round was administered just prior to the peak malaria transmission season. In **Pant 2014** [29], among 391,357 people targeted for MRP from 91 ris (villages), coverage was 85% and treatment adherence was 98%. Approximately 30,000 people were targeted for MRP in **Rybalka 1979** [30], but details on coverage and adherence were not provided.

Outcomes

Incidence of *P. vivax* infection was reported by both studies. **Pant 2014** [29] reported monthly incidence among all persons residing in intervention villages from <1 month to 10 months post-MRP (classified as <1, 1-3, and 4-12 month time periods for analysis). **Rybalka 1979** [30] reported monthly incidence for 11 months prior to MRP (pre-MRP) and for 1 to 5 months following MRP (classified as 1-3 and 4-12 months post-MRP for analysis). Data for **Rybalka 1979** [30] were provided in a graphical format (data extracted by visual estimation) with no information on the method of diagnostic confirmation.

Prevalence of *P. vivax* infection was reported in **Pant 2014** [29] at <1 month and 4 months post-MRP through cross-sectional surveys and diagnostic confirmation by microscopy. Information about how participants for cross-sectional surveys were selected was not described. Information on adverse events was available from **Pant 2014** [29] for participants receiving primaquine.

Contextual factors

Information on the human resource requirements for implementation of MRP was available from **Kondrashin 2014** [7], which provided more details on the MRP implemented in DPR Korea and reported in **Pant 2014** [29].

Excluded studies

A total of 22 article were excluded due to the following reasons: intervention was MDA with a blood stage schizonticide and a hypnozoitocidal drug (n=13), intervention did not include an 8-aminoquinoline (n=2), background interventions were not balanced across arms (n=2), no outcome data were reported (n=2), control group criteria were not met (n=1), a treatment dose of an 8-aminoquinoline was not used (n=1), and the intervention was not mass relapse prevention (n=1). Detailed reasons are provided in [Characteristics of excluded studies](#).

Risk of bias in included studies

Assessments for risk of bias for each study are summarized in **Figure 2** and **Figure 3** with support for judgements provided in the [Characteristics of included studies](#) tables.

Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria (inclusion of control population) **Pant 2014** [29] included a contemporaneous control group and was judged as low risk. **Rybalka 1979** [30] did not include a control group and was judged high risk; the baseline (pre-intervention) data collected on the population that received MRP was used for comparisons.

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Flawed measurement of exposure

Pant 2014 [29] provided MRP as directly observed treatment and was judged as low risk. **Rybalka 1979** [30] did not provide any details on how MRP was distributed or the population that received it and was judged as high risk.

Flawed measurement of outcome (outcome-level)

Both studies provided limited information on how incidence was measured. **Pant 2014** [29] was judged as unclear risk. **Rybalka 1979** [30] was scored as high risk since outcome data were provided in a graph, which had to be extracted by visual examination.

Pant 2014 [29] reported prevalence of parasitemia and was judged as high risk since details on the population selected for evaluation were not provided.

Pant 2014 [29] also reported adverse events, but since these data were only collected in the intervention group, the outcome measurement was judged as high risk of bias.

Failure to adequately control for confounding

Both studies were judged as high risk for bias due to confounding since allocation to intervention and control was not done at random and there were no data provided to assess for baseline differences in intervention and control groups.

Incomplete follow-up

Population movement in **Pant 2014** [29] was likely limited and there was a dedicated health unit for 150-200 households in study areas, so the risk of bias was low. **Rybalka 1979** [30] did not provide any details about population movement during the study period and was judged as unclear risk.

Figure 2. Risk of bias summary: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for each included study

	Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria (inclusion of control population)	Flawed measurement exposure	Flawed measurement of outcome: Incidence	Flawed measurement of outcome: Prevalence	Flawed measurement of outcome: Adverse events	Failure to adequately control confounding	Incomplete follow-up
Pant 2014							
Rybalka 1979							

Figure 3. Risk of bias graph: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies

Effects of interventions

Effects reported on *P. vivax* incidence

One study (**Pant 2014** [29]) provided data at <1 month post-MRP and reported a strong and significant reduction in incidence in MRP compared to no MRP (Rate ratio 0.07, 95% CI 0.05 to 0.08, **Figure 4**). Both studies provided data at 1-3 months post-MRP and the pooled effect showed that incidence was significantly reduced in MRP compared to no MRP (pooled rate ratio 0.08, 95% CI 0.07 to 0.08, **Figure 4**). At 4-12 months post-MRP, both studies reported significant reductions in the MRP group (pooled rate ratio 0.20, 95% CI 0.18 to 0.22, **Figure 4**).

Figure 4. Forest plot of comparison: MRP vs no MRP on incidence of *Plasmodium vivax* infection

Effects reported on *P. vivax* prevalence

Prevalence was reported by a single study (**Pant 2014** [29]) at <1 month and 4-12 months post-MRP. There ~~was~~ ~~were~~ ~~no~~ ~~significant~~s reduction in prevalence immediately following MRP (<1 month) (RR ~~0.45~~~~12~~, 95% CI 0.~~01~~~~3~~ to ~~0.15~~~~.95~~~~52~~, **Figure 5**) and ~~at~~ 4-12 months post-MRP, ~~the prevalence of P. vivax infection was similar in MRP compared to no MRP groups~~ (RR 0.~~90~~~~07~~, 95% CI 0.~~41~~~~01~~ to ~~1.99~~~~0.57~~, **Figure 5**).

Figure 5. MRP vs no MRP on prevalence of *Plasmodium vivax* infection

Adverse events

Only one study provided data on adverse events and this was only reported in the intervention group (**Pant 2014** [29]). Adverse events were monitored by self-report on cards pre-printed with possible side-effects. No cases of severe haemolysis were reported and side-effects were reported on less than 4% of 400,000 cards. Additional details are provided in the [Characteristics of included studies](#) table.

Contextual factors

Kondrashin 2014 [7] described the types and number of health care staff involved with primaquine distribution in DPRK, the outcome of which was reported in **Pant 2014** [29]:

“The personnel of the County and Ri clinic/hospitals under their Directors, Household Doctors, and Health Volunteers were all involved in primaquine distribution. The size of the allotted population for each team varied from place to place, but were on average: one to two Household Doctors, one to two senior health workers together with five to ten health volunteers for approximately 500-600 people.” (**Kondrashin 2014** [7])

The study authors also describe how side effects were identified and managed by health care staff:

“The staff of the County and Ri hospitals were instructed on possible side effects and a special form was developed and made available to health workers containing management advice which was to be used for case documentation.” (**Kondrashin 2014** [7])

Mathematical modeling data

Roy 2013 [31] uses a *P. vivax* compartmental transmission model incorporating mosquito and human components to model the potential impact of MRP in a low-endemic region of India where the local *P. vivax* strain averages 7 months to relapse. They modeled the impact of an annual mass treatment of a hypnozoiticide with 90% of the population successfully covered at the beginning of each year for 5 consecutive years. They found the *P. vivax* burden to be substantially reduced after the intervention,

ranging from a 50% drop after the first annual intervention to 95% at the end of five years. After the MRP was stopped in the simulation, the incidence gradually recovered over the subsequent 10 years.

Discussion

Summary of main results

Two non-randomized studies were included in this review: one from DPRK (**Pant 2014** [29]) and the other from Azerbaijan (**Rybalka 1979** [30]). Both studies reported malaria outcomes after mass distribution of 0.25 mg/kg of primaquine per day over 14 days to eligible children and adults who were provided medication without prior G6PD testing. The MRP in DPRK was conducted in the spring (April-May) prior to the peak transmission period (May-August), while the MRP in Azerbaijan was conducted over a three-month period from April-June (the peak transmission season was not reported).

Based on these data and in comparison to no-MRP

- At <1 month post-MRP, we do not know the effect on the incidence of *P. vivax* (very low certainty evidence) as reported by a single study (**Pant 2014** [29]).
- At 1-3 months post-MRP, we do not know the effect on the incidence of *P. vivax* (very low certainty evidence) as reported by two studies (**Rybalka 1979** [30]; **Pant 2014** [29]).
- At 4-12 months post-MRP, we do not know the effect on the incidence of *P. vivax* (very low certainty evidence) as reported by two studies (**Rybalka 1979** [30]; **Pant 2014** [29]).
- At <1 month post-MRP, we do not know the effect on the prevalence of *P. vivax* (very low certainty evidence) as reported by a single study (**Pant 2014** [29]).
- At 4-12 months post-MRP, we do not know the effect on the prevalence of *P. vivax* (very low certainty evidence) as reported by a single study (**Pant 2014** [29]).

Based only on data from the population receiving MRP, the proportion of the population reporting side effects was 4% (very low certainty evidence) as reported by a single study (**Pant 2014** [29]). Among 400,000 cards for adverse event monitoring, 4% reported at least one side-effect. No cases of severe haemolysis were reported. Reported side effects included: headache (4,291 people), epigastric pain (2,451 people), nausea and vomiting (1,801 people), dizziness (1,753 people), anorexia (1,702 people), changed urine color (254 people), black-colored urine (15 people) and other (1,098 people).

Despite the very low certainty evidence available for multiple outcomes, there was a general trend of a substantial reduction in *P. vivax* incidence following MRP and the rate ratio for the reduction decreased in the 4-12 months post-MRP compared to the 1-3 months or <1 month post-MRP. ~~There was no Parasite prevalence also decreased <1 month and 4-12 months following MRP. reduction in parasite prevalence.~~ A mathematical modeling study (**Roy 2013** [31]) suggested that MRP achieving 90% coverage with an effective hypnozoiticide given before the transmission season in India, where relapse intervals are approximately 7 months after initial infection, could reduce *P. vivax* transmission by 50%.

Overall completeness and applicability of evidence

Only two empirical studies were identified that met the inclusion criteria for this review, although narrative reports of programmatic experience with MRP are available and one mathematical study. Both empirical studies were conducted prior to 2003; both studies were conducted in temperate areas where *P. vivax* has been reported to have a long relapse period and transmission is highly seasonal [3]. Both used standard 14-day dose regimens of primaquine, and neither conducted G6PD testing prior to administration of primaquine, although background rates of G6PD deficiency were considered low.

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These findings are limited, therefore, to temperate areas of *P. vivax* transmission where the strain exhibits a long relapse periodicity and G6PD deficiency is low.

Quality of the evidence

Both studies were non-randomized and one was not controlled. Both were conducted without a prespecified protocol and both used programmatic data for measurement of exposure and outcome and lacked detail on potential confounding factors as well as information on recruitment, refusal rates, compliance, quality of diagnosis or healthcare seeking rates in the population. As a result, the confidence in the results is very low.

Potential biases in the review process

We could not assess publication bias with only two studies included in the review.

Agreements and disagreements with other studies or reviews

Narrative reports of MPPT in Azerbaijan, Tajikistan, North Afghanistan and the Democratic People's Republic of Korea found reductions between 40-72% in *P. vivax* malaria cases or incidence and observed a low frequency of severe adverse events, despite a population prevalence of G6PD deficiency as high as 39% in some areas [7]. These reports did not meet inclusion criteria for the current review. A WHO review of mass drug administration and related strategies, including mass primaquine prophylactic treatment (MPPT), in 2015 did not recommend this strategy to reduce *P. vivax* transmission although they recognized that it had been deployed to a large number of people without significant harmful effects, and that transmission of *P. vivax* had been significantly reduced although not interrupted [32].

Authors' conclusions

Implications for practice

Only two empirical studies and results from one mathematical model were included in this review on MRP. Both empirical studies were rated as having a high risk of bias and the overall body of evidence judged as having very low certainty. We do not know with any confidence whether or not MRP reduces the incidence or prevalence of *P. vivax*. Similarly, with data on adverse events only collected from the intervention arm of the study, we cannot know with any certainty the effect of MRP on adverse events. However, the proportion of the participants who reported adverse events in one study was <4% and no cases of hemolysis or AHA were reported.

Implications for research

Studies on MRP have only been reviewed from temperate countries where *P. vivax* strains exhibit long relapse periods and transmission is highly seasonal. It is not clear whether mass relapse prevention is an intervention likely to be applicable for many countries in the future given how few temperate countries remain with *P. vivax* transmission, and even DPRK is now close to eliminating malaria transmission. Therefore, the need for future research on MRP is likely to be very low.

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Characteristics of studies

Characteristics of included studies

Pant 2014

Study characteristics	
METHODS	
Study dates	2002-2003
Location(s) of study:	Kangnam, Sukchon, Sonchon, Sinchon, Hwangju, Anbyon and Panmum counties, Democratic People's Republic of Korea
Baseline malaria endemicity	<i>P. vivax</i> prevalence <1% (very low transmission)
Peak transmission season	May to August; <i>P. vivax</i> parasites are dormant Jan to April (winter). Majority (70-80%) of cases reported in a given year were infections from the previous year and the remaining are new infections.
Malaria species	<i>P. vivax</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles sinensis</i>
Entomologic inoculation rate (EIR)	Not described
Antimalarial drug resistance context	Not described
Study design	Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled study
Statistical power calculation	Not described
Clusters or groups	<p><u>Unit of non-randomized group allocation:</u> Ris (villages)</p> <p><u>Number of clusters selected:</u> 176 (91 intervention, 85 control)</p> <p><u>Analyzed:</u> 176</p> <p><u>Average cluster size:</u> 4621</p> <p><u>Design features of the clusters:</u> Villages are geographically distinct, therefore contamination across intervention and control areas is unlikely</p>
PARTICIPANTS	
Population targeted	<p><u>Total:</u> 813,232</p> <p><u>Intervention:</u> 391,357 from 91 ris</p> <p><u>Comparator:</u> 421,875 from 85 ris</p>
Eligibility	All ages 5 years and above. Pregnant women, and patients with lupus, arthritis, leukemia, hepatitis, or a history of hemolysis/hypersensitivity after taking primaquine were excluded. The control group included participants aged 5 years and above.
G6PD Testing and prevalence	No testing done, but historic data suggests G6PD prevalence between 0.5 and 2.9%
INTERVENTION	

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Antimalarial(s) and Regimen	Ages ≥ 5 years: 0.25 mg/kg per day, equaling a total of 15 mg primaquine given for 14 days (total dose: 3.5 mg/kg over 14 days)
Number of rounds and timing/dates	1 round (April 18 – May 3, 2002)
Interval	Not applicable (single round)
Duration implemented	2 weeks
Coverage by round	85.3%
Treatment adherence by round	98.4% (# completing full course/ # treated)
Comparator type	No MRP
Background/co-interventions	No co-interventions described
OUTCOMES	
Incidence of <i>P. vivax</i> infection	<u>Measurement:</u> Monthly incidence measured by microscopy at village hospitals <u>Time points:</u> post-MRP <1 month (May 2002), post-MRP 1-3 months (June-August 2002), and post-MRP 4-12 months (September 2002 to February 2003) <u>Sample size:</u> Monthly denominators not provided, assumed to be fixed (391,357 intervention, 421,875 control)
Prevalence of <i>P. vivax</i> infection	<u>Measurement:</u> Cross-sectional mass blood surveys; population sampling criteria not described <u>Time points:</u> post-MRP <1 month (May 2002) and post-MRP 4-12 months (September 2002) <u>Sample size (range):</u> 4215 to 5138 (intervention); 2994 to 3716 (control)
Adverse effects	Approximately 400,000 cards were distributed to participants in the intervention arm to monitor probable adverse effects. Less than 4% of cards reported at least one probable side-effect. The most commonly reported side-effects were headache (1%), epigastric pain (0.6%), nausea and vomiting (0.5%), dizziness (0.4%), and changed urine color or black-colored urine (0.07%). There were no cases of severe hemolysis.

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria (inclusion of control population)	Low risk	Control ris were included with the same inclusion criteria as the intervention ris.
Flawed measurement exposure	Low risk	Details provided for a task force to deliver mass relapse prevention with primaquine (directly observed treatment)
Flawed measurement of outcome: Incidence	Unclear risk	Microscopy capacity expanded throughout the study area during the study period, which suggests

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		that capacity changed over time. No details provided on how incidence was assessed, other than measurement was monthly was based on total number of malaria cases.
Flawed measurement of outcome: Prevalence	High risk	Sampling not described for cross-sectional surveys and prevalence denominators indicate that a subset of the total population was evaluated. Cases were confirmed by microscopy.
Flawed measurement of outcome: Adverse events	High risk	Measured using pre-printed cards with probable side-effects. However, cards were only distributed in the intervention group, so adverse events were not measured in the control group.
Failure to adequately control confounding	High risk	Confounding factors not described and allocation to control and intervention was not done at random. No baseline data to evaluate differences in intervention and control clusters.
Incomplete follow-up	Low risk	Incidence measured monthly in entire study area and population movement was likely minimal.

Rybalka 1979

Study characteristics	
METHODS	
Study dates	1970-1971
Location(s) of study:	Azerbaijan Soviet Socialist Republic. Pilot in five villages were described in this study (1 from Akhsuinsky District and 4 from Geokchaisky District). Following pilot, MPPT given to a large population in a Akhsuinsky District.
Baseline malaria endemicity	Prevalence or incidence are not available. The intensity of transmission in Kendoba was described as middle level based on loimopotential of epidemic year of 0.23.
Peak transmission season	Not described. Based on data provided for outcomes, the peak season appeared to be July to September 1970 and March-April 1971.
Malaria species	<i>P. vivax</i>
Vector species	Not described
Entomologic inoculation rate (EIR)	Not described
Antimalarial drug resistance context	Not described
Study design	Uncontrolled before-and-after study
Statistical power calculation	Not described

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Clusters or groups	<u>Unit of non-randomized group allocation:</u> Akhsuinsky District <u>Number of clusters selected:</u> 1 <u>Analyzed:</u> 1 <u>Average cluster size:</u> 30,000 <u>Design features of the clusters:</u> Not described
PARTICIPANTS	
Population targeted	<u>Total:</u> 30,000 (Akhsuinsky District) <u>Intervention:</u> 30,000 <u>Comparator:</u> Not applicable
Eligibility	Not described
G6PD Testing and prevalence	Not described
INTERVENTION	
Antimalarial(s) and Regimen	Age range and dose not described: primaquine given for 14 days
Number of rounds and timing/dates	1 round given to entire population between April, May, and June 1971
Interval	Not applicable (single round)
Duration implemented	3 months
Coverage by round	Not described
Treatment adherence by round	Not described
Comparator type	No MRP, pre-MRP period (same population)
Background/co-interventions	No co-interventions described
OUTCOMES	
Incidence of <i>P. vivax</i> infection	<u>Measurement:</u> Reported monthly but measurement details not described <u>Time points:</u> pre- MRP (June-April 1971), post-MRP 1-3 months (July-September 1971), and post-MRP 4-12 months (October-November 1971) <u>Sample size:</u> Monthly denominators not provided, assumed to be fixed (30,000)

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria (inclusion of control population)	High risk	No control population
Flawed measurement exposure	High risk	Limited information on how mass relapse prevention with primaquine was carried out, target population, and who received primaquine (coverage).

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Flawed measurement of outcome: Incidence	High risk	Outcome measurement not described. Assumed to be by microscopy. Additionally, outcome data was not available in tabular format and was extracted by authors based on visual examination of a hand drawn graph.
Flawed measurement of outcome: Prevalence	Unclear risk	Not applicable - prevalence not reported in this study.
Flawed measurement of outcome: Adverse events	Unclear risk	Not applicable - adverse events not reported in this study.
Failure to adequately control confounding	High risk	No confounding factors measured or reported. No control group (baseline period used as control), so high risk of bias due to confounding and confounding by time.
Incomplete follow-up	Unclear risk	Population who received mass relapse prevention assumed to be the same over time (no updated population denominators provided)

Characteristics of excluded studies

Study	Reference	Reason for exclusion
Aliev 2000	[33]	Background interventions not balanced in both arms
Aliev 2001	[34]	Background interventions not balanced in both arms
Cáceres 2004a	[35]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Cáceres 2004b	[36]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Cáceres 2005	[37]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Cáceres 2008	[38]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Chagin 1979	[39]	No outcomes, contextual factors, or mathematical modeling results reported
Henderson 1934	[40]	Not an 8-aminoquinoline
Hsiang 2013	[41]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Khaing 2016	[42]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Landier 2018	[43]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Levenson 1943	[44]	Not an 8-aminoquinoline
Lysenko 1960	[45]	Not mass relapse prevention
Lysenko 1973a	[46]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Lysenko 1973b	[47]	Control group criteria not met
Marasinghe 2020	[48]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Polevoy 1975	[49]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Singh 1968	[50]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
von Seidlein 2019a	[51]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
von Seidlein 2019b	[52]	MDA with a blood-stage schizonticide and a hypnozoiticide drug
Wojnarski 2016	[53]	Not a treatment dose of an 8-aminoquinoline
Zhang 2014	[54]	No outcomes, contextual factors, or mathematical modeling results reported

Notes: MDA = mass drug administration

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Appendix 1. Search strategy

Search Name: Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

ID	Search
#2	"antimalarial":ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#3	malaria:ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#4	MeSH descriptor: [Malaria] explode all trees
#5	MeSH descriptor: [Antimalarials] explode all trees
#6	#2 or #3 or #4 or #5
#7	"mass chemoprophylaxis" or "mass drug administration" or "mass administration"
#8	"mass screening and treatment"
#9	"mass treatment"

Database: Embase 1947-Present, updated daily

1	malaria/ or malaria control/
2	antimalarial agent/ or antimalarial*.mp.
3	(malaria or antimalarial*).ab. or (malaria or antimalarial*).ti.
4	1 or 2 or 3
5	("mass chemoprophylaxis" or "mass drug administration" or "mass administration").mp.
6	mass drug administration.mp.
7	mass treatment.mp.
8	"mass screening and treatment".mp.
9	5 or 6 or 7 or 8
10	4 and 9

Pubmed Search history

Search	Query
#1	malaria Field: Title/Abstract
#2	antimalarial*or anti-malarial* Field:Title/Abstract
#3	(malaria[MeSH Terms]) OR antimalarials[MeSH Terms]
#4	#1 or #2 or #3
#5	((mass chemoprophylaxis) OR mass drug administration) OR mass administration Field:Title/Abstract
#6	"mass screening and treatment" Field: Title/Abstract
#7	(MDA[Title/Abstract] OR MSAT[Title/Abstract] OR iMSaT[Title/Abstract])
#8	mass drug administration[MeSH Terms]
#9	#5 or #6 or #7 or #8
#10	#4 and #9

Database : LILACS

Search on:	malaria or antimalarial\$ [Words] and mass administration [Words]
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